

Frequent host-switch and gene exchange shape the evolution of *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398

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Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus ST398 is a typical 'One Health' pathobiont exemplifying multiple-host tropisms. Here we traced the evolutionary trajectory of the global accessory genome (an assembly of accessory genes) of *S. aureus* ST398 over 20 years, with the aim of identifying the mechanisms linking accessory genomes with multiple-host tropisms and the phylogenomic traits associated with severe human infections. We analyzed 1079 high-quality genomes of ST398 from 13 host species, spanning 23 years (1998–2021) and 25 countries across 5 continents, and showed that accessory gene pools of ST398 substantially expanded in the early period before 2010, aligning with the increase in the host-species spectrum. The more recent shifts of accessory genomes were mainly driven by stochastic processes. Accessory genes transferred widely across ST398 from different host-species and barely formed host-specific accessory gene pools, indicating that a host-jump of ST398 was followed shortly by another host-switch rather than a long-term co-evolution with a new host species to generate host-specific gene pools. Human-ST398 was a major recipient of accessory gene transfer, with more common gene transfer with ST398 from pig than other animals. Life-threatening exotoxin genes separately encoding Pantone-Valentine Leukocidin and the staphylococcal enterotoxin B were abundant and exclusive to human-ST398 that showed a higher evolution rate than animal-ST398. Both accessory and core genome analyses implied nutrient metabolism as a major force for ST398 evolution. Analyses of clinical data revealed a conserved evolution of ST398 along infection development within a patient, and identified a novel subtype ST398-9 (a relatively recent phylogenetic branch) and phages StauST398_5 and StauST398_1 to be closely associated with human infections. Our findings elucidate mechanisms underlying the distribution and evolution of accessory gene pools of ST398, which determine the development of multiple-host tropisms and pathogenicity.

Introduction

Pathogens jump across species boundaries to infect new host populations, which often results in disease outbreaks and epidemics [1, 2]. Globalization of livestock-trade and transportation offers pathogens an opportunity to expand to new hosts and evolve towards multiple-host tropisms [3, 4]. *Staphylococcus aureus* as one of the notorious 'multiple-host' pathobionts could infect humans and livestock to cause serious skin, soft tissue and bloodstream diseases [1, 2]. Recent studies have traced host-jump events of *S. aureus* across its evolutionary history and highlighted the importance of accessory gene acquisition for adaptation in new hosts [1, 3]. Therefore, the composition and diversity of accessory genomes might be reflective of the evolution and diversification of pathobionts, underlying multiple-host tropisms.

S. aureus multilocus sequence type 398 (ST398) was first reported in pig farms in the early 2000s [5], and it has been detected in diverse host species globally [6–9], and has become a main cause of soft tissue infections and invasive infections (e.g., pneumonia, bacteremia, and endocarditis) in humans and livestock (e.g., pig, cattle and poultry) [6, 10, 11], threatening public health and food security. Since 2007, severe infections caused by ST398 have been increasingly reported in humans with as well as without

contact with animals in different continents [8]. Methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) ST398 were found to mainly cause invasive and severe infections, while methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) were primarily associated with skin and soft tissue infections [12]. The prevalence of MRSA ST398 has substantially increased from 0% in 2002 to above 20% in 2007 in the Netherlands, and MSSA ST398 has been responsible for almost 15% of bloodstream infection cases reported in France in around 2017 [8]. Taken together, these data indicate a rapid evolution of ST398 during the last decade especially in terms of host adaptation and acquisition of specific virulence factors such as the Panton-Valentine Leukocidin, pyrogenic toxins and staphylococcal enterotoxin B [8, 13]. Therefore, elucidating the evolution of multiple-host tropisms, resistance and virulence of ST398 over 20 years since its first emergence, is important to public health and food security, but remains underexplored. Host-jumps often result in isolate diversification into different clades [1, 14], so the differences in accessory gene pools across different host species are usually ascribed to differences in clades. However, within a single clade, whether and how accessory gene pools underpin multiple-host tropisms are elusive.

S. aureus ST398, as a typical 'One Health' multiple-host pathobiont, provides an excellent opportunity to address these questions, and also address a new question: what would be the fate of the ST398 accessory genomes after a host-jump? Here, we put forward two potential hypotheses (Fig. 1A): (I) After a host-jump, the pathobiont would co-evolve with the new host species over a long period to reshape the accessory genome under new environmental stressors, probably by losing dispensable genes. Such a pattern of co-evolution with host species facilitates strain fitness [4], and the accessory genomes of such well-adapted strains would be distinguishable from those in the prior host species, reflecting diversification of accessory genomes across different host species. (II) After a host-jump, the strain would in a short time-span either jump back to the prior host species or jump spillover to a third host species (Fig. 1A). In both the events, the temporally short co-evolution would not generate a host-specific accessory gene pool. Based on the prior reports that host-jumps are usually accompanied by gene acquisition [1, 3], we assume that the accessory gene pool would expand substantially at the initial stage when a strain undergoes frequent host-jump, and then becomes relatively stable when it has disseminated to most of the possible host species (Fig. 1B). Therefore, based on the dynamics of the accessory genome pool, we could predict the stages when such host-jump events occurred.

To address the above questions and hypotheses, we conducted a population-genomic analysis of over 1000 high-quality genomes of ST398 in global, and provide an unprecedented high-resolution landscape of ST398 accessory genomes in a One Health context. The dynamics of accessory genomes over 20 years, and whether and how accessory genomes underlie multiple-host tropisms were elucidated. By integrating clinical data, we also revealed the evolution of ST398 phylogenomic traits associated with infection.

Results and Discussion

Accessory gene pool amplification in *S. aureus* ST398 correlates with host-switch

To provide a global landscape of *S. aureus* ST398 isolates in a One Health perspective, we conducted whole-genome sequencing of 146 isolates from 72 patients and 30 isolates from 6 animal species (Table 1), and combined them with 903 high-quality ST398 genomes collected from publicly available databases (Supplementary Fig. S1 and Table S1). This generated an atlas of 1079 genomes representative of 13 typical host species, over 23 years (1998–2021), and 25 countries across 5 continents (Fig. 2).

Table 1
ST398 isolate collections in this study.

Collection	No of ST398 isolates	Time of isolation	Country of isolation	Source	Clinical source
ASPIRE-ICU (NCT02413242) [37]	25	2016– 2018	Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Germany, Hungary, Serbia, Spain, The Netherlands, Turkey, UK	Humans	ETA, nose, sputum
ASPIRE-SSI (NCT02935244) [38]	57	2017– 2019	Belgium, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Serbia, Spain, The Netherlands, UK	Humans	Nose, throat, ETA, perineal, wound, blood, urine
SAATELLITE (NCT02296320) [39]	35	2014– 2017	Belgium, France, Spain, Switzerland	Humans	ETA, pleural fluid, blood
SHIP-TREND-0 and SHIP-TREND-1 [40]	18	2008– 2012 and 2016– 2019	Germany	Humans	Nose
Raafat et al. (2020) [41]	7	2016– 2017	Germany	Animal (rat)	Nose
Lekkerkerk et al. (2015) [42]	10	1998 and 2009	The Netherlands	Humans	n.r.
Lekkerkerk et al. (2015) [42]	23	2007– 2010	The Netherlands	Animal (chicken, horse, pig, veal, calve)	Nose, rectal, pharynx
Ip et al. (2005) [43]	1	2000– 2001	Hong Kong	Humans	Blood
ETA: endotracheal aspirate; n.r.: not reported.					

To profile accessory gene pools of ST398 isolates, we assembled the accessory genes that are present in some but not all the 1079 isolates (Fig. 3A). The accessory gene accumulation curves levelled off as the isolate number increased (Supplementary Fig. S2), indicating a sufficient coverage of accessory gene pools. The global accessory genome profile showed a non-random pattern, evidenced by the significant difference ($P < 0.001$) from 1000 random profiles based on a null model analysis. In the global accessory genomes (Fig. 3A), multi-drug resistance genes were dominant among antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), adherence factors predominated amongst virulence factors (VFs), and the genetic information processing was a dominant KEGG pathway. To reduce the bias caused by the uneven distribution of isolates across years, we used periods instead of years to reveal accessory genome succession (Fig. 3B-H). From the period 1998–2005 to 2006–2010, the substantial increase (by 201%) in the numbers of accessory genes aligned with the increase in the numbers of host species (by 350%), and thereafter, both remained relatively stable with minor increases (by 0–22%). Expansion in accessory gene pool correlated temporally and positively with increasing diversity of host species (Spearman's $P = 0.051$), indicating that accessory gene pool is able to provide clues to understand multiple-host tropisms. These results support our hypothesis (Fig. 1B) that the substantial expansion of accessory gene pool tends to occur during the initial stage (no later than 2010) of frequent host-jumps. The actual time of the events is likely earlier, since strain emergence would have preceded strain collection. From the period 2011–2015 to 2016–2021, the proportions of ST398 isolates significantly increased in pig and dog but decreased in cattle and poultry ($P < 0.05$ for all, Fisher's test) (Fig. 3H). The numbers of VFs and ARGs slightly decreased but that of pathway genes increased recently from the period of 2011–2015 to 2016–2021 (Fig. 3C-F). The proportion of VFs among accessory genes significantly ($P = 0.045$) decreased from 0.82% (2011–2015) to 0.52% (2016–2021), while the proportions of ARGs and pathway genes did not show any significant shifts recently. To assess whether the accessory genome succession was driven by deterministic (e.g., biotic and abiotic selection) or stochastic (e.g., genetic drift) processes, the null-model based normalized stochasticity ratio (NST), a general framework to quantify ecological stochasticity [15], was applied. NST significantly increased ($P < 0.001$ in both comparisons in Wilcoxon test) since the period of 2006–2010 (Supplementary Fig. S3A), indicating an increasing stochasticity in accessory genome changes. This finding was further supported by the significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher NST in accessory genome changes between more recent periods (Supplementary Fig. S3B). This result was in line with the low importance (6% of variable explanation in Distance-based redundancy analysis (dbRDA)) of collection year in shaping accessory genomes (Fig. 3G).

To further explore the mechanisms underlying the global distribution of accessory genomes of ST398, we assessed the impact of collection country and host species. Country is a major determinant (29% of variable explanation) in shaping accessory genomes (Fig. 3G). Countries might provide geographic barriers to restrict dispersal of accessory genes [16], also accompanied by varied environmental characteristics and anthropogenic interventions that cause selection stress on the microbial gene pools [17]. To provide additional evidence of geographic barriers, isolate dissemination across continents was inferred as previously described [18] by using a strict threshold of Mash distances < 0.0005 (Supplementary Fig. S4). The potential transfer of ST398 was continent-dependent, with more frequent

transfers between Europe and North America than between Europe and other continents, and no transfer was observed between Asia and other continents, despite a higher representation of isolates from Asia compared to America and Oceania (Fig. 4). ST398 transfer between humans and animals was more frequently detected between Oceania and Europe than between other continents. These differences might be related to the differences in human travel and farm animal trade across different continents [19].

Frequent host-switch rather than host-adaptation shapes the evolution of *S. aureus* ST398

A host-jump is not only accompanied by acquisition of novel genes but also by loss of dispensable genes along a long-term co-evolution with the new host [1]. In this context, host species is assumed to be critical to distinguish accessory genomes (hypothesis (I) in Fig. 1A). Unexpectedly, our results revealed that host species was not a determinant (only 9% of variable explanation) for accessory genomes (Fig. 3G), and thus did not support hypothesis (I). The accessory genetic elements (e.g., ARGs, VFs and phages) relevant to isolate adaptation, colonization and infection were revealed if they were present exclusively in one host species (Fig. 5A). Following the rationale of the hypothesis (I), some of host-exclusive genetic elements would be detected in all isolates of a specific host species, because these elements have been selected for isolate adaptation along a long-term co-evolution with this host species. However, our results showed that none of the host-exclusive genetic elements were present in all isolates of a specific host species (Fig. 5A). The same results were also found in all host-exclusive accessory genes (Supplementary Table S2). This result is unlikely attributed to ST398 resistance to selection of host species, because the accessory gene pool expanded as the increasing diversity of host species (Fig. 3B and E). A probable explanation is then hypothesis (II) that the host-jump is shortly followed by jump-back and/or jump-spillover (Fig. 1), so that there would be insufficient time for co-evolution with a novel host species to generate a host-specific accessory gene pool. Mutations in the core genome are another determinant of microbial adaptation in host species [20, 21]. However, host species barely (4%) determined the variations of ST398 core genome phylogeny based on single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) (Supplementary Fig. S5 and S6), further corroborating the little impact of host co-evolution on the ST398 core genome. Such an evolutionary trajectory might be the result of increased globalization of livestock-trade and transportation, and anthropogenic intervention, which increases opportunities for direct/indirect contacts of pathobionts with different host species.

To provide further evidence of a frequent host-switch of ST398, we traced the potential transfer of accessory genes of ST398 across different host species. A wide dissemination of accessory genes across different host species was revealed with each host species showing gene exchange with 5–11 other host species (Fig. 6A and Supplementary Fig. S7). Such wide gene exchange among ST398 across host-species is probably because of the close phylogenetic relatedness among ST398 isolates from various sources, which facilitates this process [22, 23]. Our results showed that humans and cattle were the most common hosts where ST398 acquired and donated accessory genes, respectively (Fig. 6A). This indicated that humans were potentially a major donor for ST398 jumps to other host species, because the genes acquired from isolates in other host species would facilitate jumps into these host

species. A large-scale survey of host-jumps of *S. aureus* based on isolate phylogeny also found humans to be a major donor of jumps to other host species [1].

Despite the wide transfer of accessory genes of ST398, the transfer tended to be host-species dependent. For example, gene transfer between humans and pig was more common (13% and 10% in both directions, respectively) than between humans and other host species (mean 10% and 8% in both directions, respectively) (Fig. 6A). To provide further evidence for the above finding and reduce the bias caused by uneven sample distribution across different host species, network analysis based on individual isolate level was applied. Similar accessory genomes were more frequently detected between ST398 from humans and pigs than between any other host species (Fig. 6B and Supplementary Fig. S8), further supporting the above finding. The first emergence of ST398 was in pig farms [5], and instances of ST398 transfer between human and pig have been frequently reported [5, 24]. Interestingly, some isolates from different countries and years also showed similar accessory genomes, indicating that gene exchange might occur through an ecologically shared accessory gene pool. Smillie et al demonstrated that bacteria from a similar ecological niche are more likely to share accessory genetic elements than those from distinct environments, probably by gene acquisitions from a shared pool of mobile DNA [16]. Taken together, our findings point to the complexity of (co-)evolutionary trajectories governing ST398 multiple-host tropisms.

Human-ST398 is marked by specific VFs and ARGs

Exotoxin genes *lukS-PV* and *lukF-PV* encoding the Panton-Valentine Leukocidin, a cytotoxin that causes leukocyte destruction and tissue necrosis, and *seb* encoding the staphylococcal enterotoxin B, implicated in massive food poisoning and marked as a bioterrorism threat [25], as well as ARGs of *aph(3')-IIIa* (conferring resistance to aminoglycoside) and *tetO* (conferring resistance to tetracycline), were abundant and exclusive to ST398 in humans. Among the ARGs and VFs that were detected in multiple host species, *ermC* (conferring resistance to macrolide-lincosamide-streptogramin) and *parC* (conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones), and *sak* (encoding staphylokinase), *scn* (encoding staphylococcal complement inhibitor) and *chp* (encoding chemotaxis inhibitory protein) were significantly associated with human isolates compared to animal isolates ($P < 0.05$ in all, Supplementary Fig. S9 and Table S3). These VFs are important immune modulators [26]. Most of human-ST398 exclusively harboring *lukS-PV* and *lukF-PV* were not MRSA, except two isolates that carried *mecA* separately with mobile elements SCC*mec* IV, V and VII (Supplementary Table S4). Although *S. aureus* isolates harboring *lukS-PV* and *lukF-PV* have been reported to transfer between humans and animals [27], our global surveillance of ST398 did not identify such instances. *MecA* was detected in most ST398 isolates interspersed among different host species but not in the relatively recent phylogenetic branches (e.g., ST398-9 and ST398-10), generally aligning with the distribution of the SCC*mec* (Fig. 7A and Supplementary Table S4). Both the numbers of genomic islands and ARG-carrying plasmids were higher in poultry-ST398 than in other host species (Supplementary Fig. S10). Poultry pathogens have been found to harbor novel mobile genetic elements that were not detected in humans pathogens [28]. Among all the ARGs carried by plasmids, genes conferring resistance to tetracycline were most frequently

detected, implying a high transfer potential of resistance to this antibiotic class. Tetracycline is one of the major antimicrobials used in farms and tetracycline resistance widely distributes among ST398 [29]. Accessory genome co-evolution analysis revealed that the co-evolution events among ARGs, VFs, plasmids and insertion sequences occurred more frequently among human isolates than animal isolates (Supplementary Fig. S11), aligning well with a higher rate ($P < 0.001$) of gene exchange among human isolates (Supplementary Fig. S12). This indicates a potentially higher evolution/diversification rate among human isolates, which was further supported by a higher ($P < 0.001$) SNP dissimilarity among human isolates than animal isolates (Supplementary Fig. S13).

Nutrient availability and metabolism drive global diversification of *S. aureus* ST398

Among the global genomes of ST398 ($n = 1079$), we utilized the fast BAPS algorithm based on hierarchical Bayesian clustering analysis [30], and *de novo* detected 26 subtypes based on core genomes (Fig. 7A and Supplementary Fig. S5). Isolates were distinguished by subtypes in the phylogenetic tree, and the variation of core genome phylogeny was explained maximally by subtype (68%), much higher than by country (18%), the previously defined clade (Supplementary Table S5, see Methods) (10%), host species (4%) and year (3%) (Supplementary Fig. S6). Therefore, the subtypes could reflect the global diversification of ST398 core genomes. To reveal the major differences across subtypes, a consensus sequence among the isolates within a subtype was generated as the representative sequence for this subtype, and 177 SNPs across these representative sequences were detected (Supplementary Table S6). Most of these SNPs occurred in genes involved in carbohydrate metabolism ($n = 15$), followed by translation ($n = 12$) (Fig. 7B and Supplementary Fig. S14). When grouping host-exclusive genes into pathways, most were also involved in metabolic pathways (43%), such as energy metabolism and carbohydrate metabolism (Fig. 5B). These results together indicated that the global diversification of ST398 mainly occurred in nutrient metabolism pathways. The differences in lactose metabolism and carbon metabolisms have been found to be separately linked to genome diversification of *S. aureus* [1] and *Bathyarchaeia* (one of the most abundant microorganisms on earth) [31]. Nutrient availability regulates microbial niches and interplays (e.g., competition and cooperation) [32], and thus is probably a major force for microbial diversification. Among nutrient metabolism, carbohydrate metabolism seemed a key factor for diversification of ST398 (Fig. 5B and Fig. 7B). Carbohydrate is a critical nutrient to regulate microbial growth and responses to perturbations [33], and the differences in microbial carbohydrate metabolism probably reflect differences in microbial realized niches [34].

Phylogenomic characteristics of *S. aureus* ST398 associated with infection

To reveal the infection-related evolution and succession of ST398, we narrowed analyses to isolates ($n = 146$) from patients ($n = 72$) whose clinical demographics were available (Supplementary Table S7). Most isolates showed a conserved evolution and succession along the duration of hospitalization of the host-patients, except the two isolates from patient 20007430011 that showed an obvious jump across tree branches (143 SNPs) (Fig. 8). The two isolates were collected separately from blood and endotracheal aspirate within a four-day interval. Since a similar sample collection pattern also occurred in the other

patients, it is unlikely that the phylogenetic jump was linked to the collection pattern and more probably it might be related to rare events of phylogenetic diversification. Such diversification has also been found in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ST15 isolated from patients during hospitalization [18]. In general, the isolates were highly clustered together based on the host patients ($P = 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.80$, dbRDA, Supplementary Fig. S15), despite infection status, body sites, countries, years, clades or subtypes, with isolates from the same patient (except 20007430011) showing a low dissimilarity with less than 46 SNPs (Supplementary Fig. S16). These results altogether indicate a conserved phylogenomic evolution of ST398 within a patient.

To explore phylogenomic characteristics of ST398 associated with infection, we compared isolates from patients who developed infections with ST398 to those that remained colonized. To avoid overrepresentation of isolates from a patient, and given the observed conserved phylogenetic evolution of isolates within a patient, only one isolate from each patient was included in the analysis. The differences between infection and colonization isolates were mainly reflected in accessory genomes but not in core genomes (Supplementary Fig. S17), with infection isolates showing a significantly lower rate ($P < 0.0001$) of gene exchange (Supplementary Fig. S18). Correlation analyses based on two independent approaches showed that the clade EM-HA-ST398 ($P < 0.05$), subtype ST398-9 ($0.05 < P < 0.1$), and the phages StauST398_5 and StauST398_1 ($0.05 < P < 0.1$) were closely associated with infection development (Supplementary Fig. S19). The clade EM-HA-ST398 defined human-derived ST398 isolates that harbored both StauST398_4 and StauST398_5 (Supplementary Table S5) [6, 8, 35]. Both EM-HA-ST398 and StauST398_5 have been reported to be associated with invasive infections in humans [8, 35]. ST398-9 subtype is a relatively recent branch of ST398 global diversification (Fig. 7A), implying ST398's evolution towards infectiousness. StauST398_1 has been previously detected in ST398 [35], but its relatedness to ST398 infection has been rarely reported. These phylogenomic characteristics of infection isolates detected in this study provided novel avenues for characterizing the molecular basis of ST398 infection. There were no statistical correlations of ARGs, VFs, plasmids or insertion sequences with infection (Supplementary Fig. S19). However, we could not completely rule out their associations with infection, because the patients included developed diverse types of infection and were from different countries (Fig. 8), where phylogenomic characteristics of ST398 associated with infection might differ. Thus, a global-scale clinical study to investigate given types of infection in specific regions is warranted. Although global surveillance of pathogens is widely favored [1, 36], such studies need to take into account the biases caused by uneven sample distribution across different regions, time and host species. In order to minimize the impact of such biases on our results, we used several mitigation approaches such as normalized proportions, multiple independent analysis approaches, and isolate-level analyses.

This study, using a One Health perspective, provides a global high-resolution landscape of diversity and evolution of accessory genomes of a typical multiple-host pathobiont over 20 years. The low-level differentiation of ST398 accessory genomes across different host species indicated that a host-jump tended to be followed shortly by jump-back or jump-spillover rather than a long-term co-evolution with a

new host species to generate host-specific gene pools. This pattern has already persisted and is contemporarily prevalent, shaping the evolution of *S. aureus* ST398 in humans and livestock.

Methods

Collection and sequencing of ST398 isolates

We incorporated 176 *S. aureus* ST398 isolates (separately from 72 patients and 6 animal species) from clinical trials of ASPIRE-ICU (NCT02413242) [37], ASPIRE-SSI (NCT02935244) [38], SAATELLITE (NCT 02296320) [39], SHIP-TREND-0 and SHIP-TREND-1 [40], and studies from Raafat et al. [41], Lekkerkerk et al. [42] and Ip et al. [43], as outlined in Table 1. The patient demographics were collected accordingly (Supplementary Table S7).

The ASPIRE-ICU (NCT02413242) was a prospective observational cohort study, conducted across 30 intensive care units (ICUs) in 11 European countries between 2015 and 2018. This multicenter epidemiological study aimed to explore the occurrence and risk factors associated with ICU pneumonia caused by *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [37]. ASPIRE-SSI (NCT02935244) was a multicenter, observational and prospective cohort study that recruited 5004 surgical patients across 33 hospitals in 10 European countries between 2016 and 2019, to assess the incidence and risk factors associated with surgical site and bloodstream infections caused by *S. aureus* in Europe [38]. SAATELLITE (NCT 02296320) was a multicenter, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, phase 2 pilot study conducted across 31 hospitals in 9 countries to investigate the efficacy of a human monoclonal antibody against *S. aureus* alpha toxin on VAP prevention in mechanically ventilated adult subjects [39]. SHIP-TREND (SHIP-TREND-0 and SHIP-TREND-1) was a population-based epidemiological study in Western Pomerania (in the northeast of Germany), to assess the prevalence and incidence of common risk factors, subclinical disorders and clinical diseases and investigate their complex associations [40].

Raafat et al. [41] explored *S. aureus* ST398 carriage in rats. Lekkerkerk et al. [42] investigated the origin of livestock-associated ST398 from humans lacking direct contact with livestock. Ip et al. [43] examined epidemic clones of ST398 causing bacteraemia in patients in Hong Kong hospitals during the period 2000 and 2001. Details in these clinical trials and studies have been shown in the Supplementary Methods.

These 176 isolates were subjected to DNA extraction by the MasterPure Complete DNA and RNA Purification kit (Epicenter, United States). Library and sample preparation were conducted using Nextera XT sample preparation kit, followed by whole genome sequencing using MiSeq (Illumina, United States). For the raw sequencing data, the BacPipe (v.2.10), a whole genome analysis pipeline [44], was applied with default parameters for quality control, genome assembly and MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing) detection. The MLST detection confirmed that all the 176 isolates are ST398. CheckM (1.1.2) [45] was used to assess the completeness and contamination of the assembled genomes. All the 176 genomes reached a high quality, with genome completeness > 98% and contamination < 10%.

Global collection of publicly available ST398 genomic data

All the publicly available sequencing samples of ST398 isolates (n = 2752 including 1968 raw sequencing samples and 784 assembled genome samples) deposited in NCBI until 5th November 2021 were retrieved. The metadata (e.g., collection country, year and host species) were also retrieved accordingly. We assembled the raw sequencing data (n = 1968) and evaluated their MLST by using BacPipe, and successfully achieved 1684 ST398 genomes. Then, we evaluated the MLST of the assembled genomes (n = 784) and finally confirmed 670 ST398 genomes. For these confirmed ST398 genomes (n = 2354), we further evaluated genome completeness and contamination, by using CheckM, and only kept 2318 ST398 genomes with completeness > 98% and contamination < 10%. Based on the metadata, we removed duplicate samples with shared biosample ID between assembled genome samples and raw sequencing samples in NCBI, and only kept the unique samples with available information in all of collection country, collection year and host species. Finally, we achieved 903 high quality genome samples used for the following analyses (Supplementary Fig. S1 and Table S1).

Analysis of genomes

In total, this study included 1079 high quality genomes of ST398 in global (Fig. 2). The Prokka (v.1.14.5) [46] was used with default parameters for genome annotation. The EggNOG-emapper (v.2.1.7) [47] was used with default parameters for the gene annotation and KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) metabolic pathway profiling of genomes. The detections of antibiotic resistance genes based on the comprehensive antibiotic resistance database [48], virulence genes based on virulence factor database [49], and plasmids based on the PlasmidFinder database [50], were conducted in the BacPipe with default parameters. The phage genes within genomes were detected by blast-based searching (E-value $\leq 10^{-10}$, coverage = 100%, identity = 100%), based on the PHASTER database [51]. Within a ST398 genome, if > 50% of phage genes from a phage were detected, we proposed the existence of this phage. The insertion sequences were detected by blast-based searching (E-value $\leq 10^{-10}$, coverage $\geq 60\%$, identity $\geq 60\%$) based on the ISfinder database [52]. Mash distance [53] that is able to estimate the genome dissimilarity was calculated between pairwise genomes. Based on the KEGG profiles of genomes, the clustering analysis of genomes using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity with the method = "average" was conducted in the vegan package in R (v.4.1.2).

Phylogenetic analysis

To generate pangenome and core genome alignment of isolates, Roary (v.3.13.0) [54] was used with a threshold for a core gene that must be present in 100% of isolates. The accessory genes of a isolate were the genes that were present in this isolate but not in all the isolates, and the accessory genome of this isolate was the assemblage of its accessory genes. Based on the core genome alignment, the Gubbins (v.2.4.1) [55] was applied with default parameters to generate SNPs excluding recombination. The SNPs file was used to generate the maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree by using RAxML-NG (v.1.1.0) [56] with the model of "GTR + G" and the other default parameters. The phylogenetic tree was

visualized by the ggtree package in R. The R package panstripe was used to calculate the association between the core genome branch length and the number of gene exchange events.

ST398 subtypes and clades

To de novo subdivide ST398 isolates into different subtypes, the fast BAPS algorithm based on hierarchical Bayesian clustering analysis [30] was used for the core genome alignment of the global isolates. The optimized hyperparameter was first generated by the function of “optimise_prior”, and then was used for the Bayesian hierarchical clustering. To excavate the phylogenomic differences among different subtypes, a consensus sequence among the isolates within a subtype was generated by EMBOSS (v.6.6.0.0) to be the representative sequence for this subtype. The SNPs among the representative sequences of different subtypes were generated by the SNP-sites (v.2.5.1) [57]. The four clades (Animal-LA, Humans-LA, EM-HA-ST398 and AN-HA-ST398) of ST398 isolates were classified based on whether the isolate was collected from humans or animal and whether it harbored phages StauST398_4 or StauST398_5 (Supplementary Table S5) [6, 35]. The co-evolution analysis of accessory genomes was conducted by using the DeCoTUR [58], with Mash distance, and “fraction” = 0.02.

Population-genomic association analysis

To explore isolate phylogenomic characteristics associated with infection, the 146 isolates from 72 hospitalized patients were used for associated analyses. To avoid overrepresentation, only one isolate from each patient was included for this analysis. For infected patients from whom multiple isolates were collected during hospitalization, the isolate from the collection timepoint that was the earliest time of the patient to document infection was selected as infective isolate. For non-infected patients (without ST398 infection) from whom multiple isolates were collected for screening, the isolate from the earliest collection timepoint was selected as colonizing only isolate. In total, 19 isolates linked with clinically documented infections (in 19 patients), and 53 colonizing only isolates from 53 non-infected patients were finally used for the associated analysis. The logic regression analysis between clinical traits (infection-related or colonizing only isolates) and isolate phylogenomic characteristics (e.g., subtypes, clades, genes and plasmids) was conducted with the stats package in R. To further confirm the results of the associated analysis above, the independence test that could be on arbitrary scales was conducted between clinical traits and isolate phylogenomic characteristics, by using the coin package in R. To explore isolate phylogenomic characteristics associated with human or animal ST398, the same analysis approaches were used for the global isolates.

Network analysis

To reveal the interconnections among accessory genomes of ST398 isolates across different host species, collection countries and years in a global context, the accessory genomes of the global isolates were used for network analyses. The CoNet, a robust ensemble-based network analysis tool for detecting nonrandom interconnections among different taxa with multiple measures [59], was used to detect the interconnections across isolates based on the similarity of their accessory genomes. Specifically, two different methods (Bray-Curtis and Kullback-Leibler dissimilarity measures) were

simultaneously used to calculate pairwise interconnections among isolates. Initial thresholds for the two measures were selected to retrieve 1000 highest and lowest scoring edges. Permutation (including renormalization) and bootstrap distributions were generated with 100 iterations each to achieve measure-specific *P* values. The measure-specific *P* values (i.e., *P* values in the two methods) were merged by using Brown's method [60], and the merged *P* values were multiple-testing-corrected with the "BH" method [61]. Only the interconnections with a corrected $P < 0.01$ and both dissimilarity measures < 0.005 were kept. To further confirm the results of the network analysis above, a different approach was conducted for the network analysis. The Jaccard weighted dissimilarity among isolates based on their accessory genomes was calculated in package *vegan* in R. Only the interconnections with a dissimilarity < 0.005 were kept. The Cytoscape (v.3.9.0) [62] was used to visualize the networks.

Source-tracker analysis

To explore potential transmission of accessory genes across different host species, source-tracker analysis based on Bayesian modeling [63] was applied. Within the global isolate pool, the accessory genes could be gained or lost by isolates from different host species and thus were assumed to be transferable across isolates from different host species. Based on this assumption, isolates from any host species have potential to transmit accessory genes to isolates from other hosts, as well as to gain accessory genes from isolates in other hosts directly or indirectly. The accessory genomes of isolates were used as input for Bayesian analysis with default parameters (e.g., rarefaction = 1000, train_rarefaction = 1000 and iteration = 100). Only the potential transmissions with proportions $> 5\%$ were kept.

Statistical analysis

Wilcoxon rank sum test and distance-based redundancy analysis were conducted in *vegan* package in R. The global maps were created in the R packages of *ggplot2* and *scatterpie*. The longitude and latitude information of countries were utilized through the function `map_data('world')` in the R package *ggplot2*. Based on accessory genomes, null-model based normalized stochasticity ratio (NST) [15] was calculated with the function `tNST (dist.method="bray", abundance.weighted = TRUE, rand = 1000, null.model= "PF")` in the R package *NST* to show the importance of stochastic processes in the changes of accessory genomes of ST398 isolates. Plots were visualized in *ggplot2* package in R. SNP dissimilarity between isolates was calculated in package *Biostrings* in R.

Declarations

Data availability

Illumina sequencing datasets generated for this study are available at the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under BioProject no. PRJNA1079020.

Ethics

In this study, isolates from clinical trials and research studies were used. The clinical trial protocols were approved by institutional or ethics review boards at each participating hospital or country. All participants, or their legal representative, provided written informed consent. The animal studies, were approved by an institutional animal care and use committee.

Author contributions

Study concept: SMK, QL. Clinical data and sample collection: LT, DR, SH, CL, FP, HSJ, BF, BS, MTE, MB, HG, WJVW, JAJWK, SMK; Sequencing: JV, CL, BBX, LT, DET; Data analysis: QL; Data interpretation: QL, SMK, SKS; Writing of first draft: QL; Manuscript revisions: SMK, QL, LT, SKS, MNN, YG, TEVDS; Manuscript final draft: All authors.

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References

1. Richardson EJ, Bacigalupe R, Harrison EM, Weinert LA, Lycett S, Vrieling M et al (2018) Gene exchange drives the ecological success of a multi-host bacterial pathogen. *Nat Ecol Evol* 2:1468–1478
2. Woolhouse ME, Haydon DT, Antia R (2005) Emerging pathogens: the epidemiology and evolution of species jumps. *Trends Ecol Evol* 20:238–244
3. Yebra G, Harling-Lee JD, Lycett S, Aarestrup FM, Larsen G, Cavaco LM et al (2022) Multiclonal human origin and global expansion of an endemic bacterial pathogen of livestock. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 119:e2211217119

4. Woolhouse ME, Webster JP, Domingo E, Charlesworth B, Levin BR (2002) Biological and biomedical implications of the co-evolution of pathogens and their hosts. *Nat Genet* 32:569–577
5. Armand-Lefevre L, Ruimy R, Andremont A (2005) Clonal comparison of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from healthy pig farmers, human controls, and pigs. *Emerg Infect Dis* 11:711
6. Uhlemann AC, Porcella SF, Trivedi S, Sullivan SB, Hafer C, Kennedy AD et al (2012) Identification of a highly transmissible animal-independent *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398 clone with distinct genomic and cell adhesion properties. *mBio.* ;3
7. Uhlemann AC, McAdam PR, Sullivan SB, Knox JR, Khiabani H, Rabadan R et al (2017) Evolutionary Dynamics of Pandemic Methicillin-Sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398 and Its International Spread via Routes of Human Migration. *mBio.* ;8
8. Laumay F, Benchetrit H, Corvaglia A-R, van der Mee-Marquet N, François P (2021) The *Staphylococcus aureus* CC398 Lineage: An Evolution Driven by the Acquisition of Prophages and Other Mobile Genetic Elements. *Genes.* ;12
9. Smith TC, Pearson N (2011) The emergence of *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398. *Vector-Borne Zoonotic Dis* 11:327–339
10. Nemati M, Hermans K, Lipinska U, Denis O, Deplano A, Struelens M et al (2008) Antimicrobial resistance of old and recent *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from poultry: first detection of livestock-associated methicillin-resistant strain ST398. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 52:3817–3819
11. Schnitt A, Lienen T, Wichmann-Schauer H, Cuny C, Tenhagen B-A (2020) The occurrence and distribution of livestock-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398 on German dairy farms. *J Dairy Sci* 103:11806–11819
12. Bouiller K, Bertrand X, Hocquet D, Chirouze C (2020) Human infection of methicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* CC398: a review. *Microorganisms* 8:1737
13. He C, Xu S, Zhao H, Hu F, Xu X, Jin S et al (2018) Leukotoxin and pyrogenic toxin Superantigen gene backgrounds in bloodstream and wound *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from eastern region of China. *BMC Infect Dis* 18:1–10
14. Fitzgerald JR (2012) Livestock-associated *Staphylococcus aureus*: origin, evolution and public health threat. *Trends Microbiol* 20:192–198
15. Ning D, Deng Y, Tiedje JM, Zhou J (2019) A general framework for quantitatively assessing ecological stochasticity. *PNAS* 116:16892–16898
16. Smillie CS, Smith MB, Friedman J, Cordero OX, David LA, Alm EJ (2011) Ecology drives a global network of gene exchange connecting the human microbiome. *Nature* 480:241–244
17. Simonsen AK (2022) Environmental stress leads to genome streamlining in a widely distributed species of soil bacteria. *ISME J* 16:423–434
18. Pham MH, Hoi LT, Beale MA, Khokhar FA, Hoa NT, Musicha P et al (2023) Evidence of widespread endemic populations of highly multidrug resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in hospital settings in Hanoi, Vietnam: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Microbe* 4:e255–e263

19. Baker RE, Mahmud AS, Miller IF, Rajeev M, Rasambainarivo F, Rice BL et al (2022) Infectious disease in an era of global change. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 20:193–205
20. Price LB, Stegger M, Hasman H, Aziz M, Larsen J, Andersen PS et al (2012) *Staphylococcus aureus* CC398: host adaptation and emergence of methicillin resistance in livestock. *mBio.* ;3
21. He L, Zheng HX, Wang Y, Le KY, Liu Q, Shang J et al (2018) Detection and analysis of methicillin-resistant human-adapted sequence type 398 allows insight into community-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* evolution. *Genome Med* 10:5
22. Forster SC, Liu J, Kumar N, Gulliver EL, Gould JA, Escobar-Zepeda A et al (2022) Strain-level characterization of broad host range mobile genetic elements transferring antibiotic resistance from the human microbiome. *Nat Commun* 13:1445
23. Forsberg KJ, Patel S, Gibson MK, Lauber CL, Knight R, Fierer N et al (2014) Bacterial phylogeny structures soil resistomes across habitats. *Nature* 509:612–616
24. Pirolo M, Visaggio D, Gioffrè A, Artuso I, Gherardi M, Pavia G et al (2019) Unidirectional animal-to-human transmission of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* ST398 in pig farming; evidence from a surveillance study in southern Italy. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control* 8:1–10
25. Leggiadro RJ (2000) The threat of biological terrorism: a public health and infection control reality. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol* 21:53–56
26. van Wamel WJ, Rooijackers SH, Ruyken M, van Kessel KP, van Strijp JA (2006) The innate immune modulators staphylococcal complement inhibitor and chemotaxis inhibitory protein of *Staphylococcus aureus* are located on β -hemolysin-converting bacteriophages. *J Bacteriol* 188:1310–1315
27. Van Duijkeren E, Wolfhagen M, Heck M, Wannet W (2005) Transmission of a Pantone-Valentine leucocidin-positive, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* strain between humans and a dog. *J Clin Microbiol* 43:6209–6211
28. Lowder BV, Guinane CM, Ben Zakour NL, Weinert LA, Conway-Morris A, Cartwright RA et al (2009) Recent human-to-poultry host jump, adaptation, and pandemic spread of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences.* ;106:19545–19550
29. Lozano C, Aspiroz C, Ara M, Gómez-Sanz E, Zarazaga M, Torres C (2011) Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) ST398 in a farmer with skin lesions and in pigs of his farm: clonal relationship and detection of *lnu* (A) gene. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 17:923–927
30. Tonkin-Hill G, Lees JA, Bentley SD, Frost SD, Corander J (2019) Fast hierarchical Bayesian analysis of population structure. *Nucleic Acids Res* 47:5539–5549
31. Hou J, Wang Y, Zhu P, Yang N, Liang L, Yu T et al (2023) Taxonomic and carbon metabolic diversification of Bathyarchaeia during its coevolution history with early Earth surface environment. *Sci Adv* 9:eadf5069
32. Hooper LV, Midtvedt T, Gordon JI (2002) How host-microbial interactions shape the nutrient environment of the mammalian intestine. *Annu Rev Nutr* 22:283–307

33. Ostrem Loss E, Thompson J, Cheung PLK, Qian Y, Venturelli OS (2023) Carbohydrate complexity limits microbial growth and reduces the sensitivity of human gut communities to perturbations. *Nat Ecol Evol* 7:127–142
34. Lozupone CA, Hamady M, Cantarel BL, Coutinho PM, Henrissat B, Gordon JI et al (2008) The convergence of carbohydrate active gene repertoires in human gut microbes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences.* ;105:15076–15081
35. van der Mee-Marquet N, Corvaglia AR, Valentin AS, Hernandez D, Bertrand X, Girard M et al (2013) Analysis of prophages harbored by the human-adapted subpopulation of *Staphylococcus aureus* CC398. *Infect Genet Evol* 18:299–308
36. Gardy JL, Loman NJ (2018) Towards a genomics-informed, real-time, global pathogen surveillance system. *Nat Rev Genet* 19:9–20
37. Paling FP, Troeman DP, Wolkewitz M, Kalyani R, Prins DR, Weber S et al (2017) Rationale and design of ASPIRE-ICU: a prospective cohort study on the incidence and predictors of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* pneumonia in the ICU. *BMC Infect Dis* 17:1–6
38. Troeman DP, Hazard D, Timbermont L, Malhotra-Kumar S, Van Werkhoven CH, Wolkewitz M et al (2023) Postoperative *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in patients with and without preoperative colonization. *JAMA Netw open* 6:e2339793–e2339793
39. François B, Jafri HS, Chastre J, Sánchez-García M, Eggimann P, Dequin P-F et al (2021) Efficacy and safety of suvratoxumab for prevention of *Staphylococcus aureus* ventilator-associated pneumonia (SAATELLITE): a multicentre, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, phase 2 pilot trial. *Lancet Infect Dis* 21:1313–1323
40. Holtfreter S, Grumann D, Balau V, Barwich A, Kolata J, Goehler A et al (2016) Molecular epidemiology of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the general population in Northeast Germany: results of the study of health in Pomerania (SHIP-TREND-0). *J Clin Microbiol* 54:2774–2785
41. Raafat D, Mrochen DM, Al’Sholui F, Heuser E, Ryll R, Pritchett-Corning KR et al (2020) Molecular epidemiology of methicillin-susceptible and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in wild, captive and laboratory rats: Effect of habitat on the nasal *S. aureus* population. *Toxins* 12:80
42. Lekkerkerk W, Van Wamel W, Snijders S, Willems R, van Duijkeren E, Broens E et al (2015) What is the origin of livestock-associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* clonal complex 398 isolates from humans without livestock contact? An epidemiological and genetic analysis. *J Clin Microbiol* 53:1836–1841
43. Ip M, Yung R, Ng T, Luk W, Tse C, Hung P et al (2005) Contemporary methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* clones in Hong Kong. *J Clin Microbiol* 43:5069–5073
44. Xavier BB, Mysara M, Bolzan M, Ribeiro-Gonçalves B, Alako BT, Harrison P et al (2020) BacPipe: A rapid, user-friendly whole-genome sequencing pipeline for clinical diagnostic bacteriology. *iScience* 23:100769
45. Parks DH, Imelfort M, Skennerton CT, Hugenholtz P, Tyson GW (2015) CheckM: assessing the quality of microbial genomes recovered from isolates, single cells, and metagenomes. *Genome Res*

46. Seemann T (2014) Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation. *Bioinformatics* 30:2068–2069
47. Huerta-Cepas J, Szklarczyk D, Heller D, Hernández-Plaza A, Forslund SK, Cook H et al (2019) eggNOG 5.0: a hierarchical, functionally and phylogenetically annotated orthology resource based on 5090 organisms and 2502 viruses. *Nucleic Acids Res* 47:D309–D314
48. Alcock BP, Huynh W, Chalil R, Smith KW, Raphenya AR, Wlodarski MA et al (2023) CARD 2023: expanded curation, support for machine learning, and resistome prediction at the Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database. *Nucleic Acids Res* 51:D690–D699
49. Liu B, Zheng D, Zhou S, Chen L, Yang J (2022) VFDB 2022: a general classification scheme for bacterial virulence factors. *Nucleic Acids Res* 50:D912–D917
50. Carattoli A, Hasman H (2020) PlasmidFinder and in silico pMLST: identification and typing of plasmid replicons in whole-genome sequencing (WGS). *Horizontal Gene Transfer: Methods and Protocols*. :285–294
51. Arndt D, Grant JR, Marcu A, Sajed T, Pon A, Liang Y et al (2016) PHASTER: a better, faster version of the PHAST phage search tool. *Nucleic Acids Res* 44:W16–W21
52. Siguier P, Pérochon J, Lestrade L, Mahillon J, Chandler M (2006) ISfinder: the reference centre for bacterial insertion sequences. *Nucleic Acids Res* 34:D32–D36
53. Ondov BD, Treangen TJ, Melsted P, Mallonee AB, Bergman NH, Koren S et al (2016) Mash: fast genome and metagenome distance estimation using MinHash. *Genome Biol.* ;17
54. Page AJ, Cummins CA, Hunt M, Wong VK, Reuter S, Holden MT et al (2015) Roary: rapid large-scale prokaryote pan genome analysis. *Bioinformatics* 31:3691–3693
55. Croucher NJ, Page AJ, Connor TR, Delaney AJ, Keane JA, Bentley SD et al (2015) Rapid phylogenetic analysis of large samples of recombinant bacterial whole genome sequences using Gubbins. *Nucleic Acids Res* 43:e15–e15
56. Stamatakis A (2014) RAxML version 8: a tool for phylogenetic analysis and post-analysis of large phylogenies. *Bioinformatics* 30:1312–1313
57. Page AJ, Taylor B, Delaney AJ, Soares J, Seemann T, Keane JA et al (2016) SNP-sites: rapid efficient extraction of SNPs from multi-FASTA alignments. *bioRxiv*. :038190
58. Mehta RS, Petit RA III, Read TD, Weissman DB (2023) Detecting patterns of accessory genome coevolution in *Staphylococcus aureus* using data from thousands of genomes. *BMC Bioinformatics* 24:243
59. Lima-Mendez G, Faust K, Henry N, Decelle J, Colin S, Carcillo F et al (2015) Determinants of community structure in the global plankton interactome. *Science*. ;348
60. Brown MB (1975) 400: A method for combining non-independent, one-sided tests of significance. *Biometrics*. :987–992
61. Benjamini Y, Hochberg Y (1995) Controlling the false discovery rate: a practical and powerful approach to multiple testing. *J R Stat Soc Ser B* 57:289–300

62. Shannon P, Markiel A, Ozier O, Baliga NS, Wang JT, Ramage D et al (2003) Cytoscape: a software environment for integrated models of biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Res* 13:2498–2504
63. Knights D, Kuczynski J, Charlson ES, Zaneveld J, Mozer MC, Collman RG et al (2011) Bayesian community-wide culture-independent microbial source tracking. *Nat Methods* 8:761–763

Figures

Figure 1

Conceptual framework describing the relationship between isolate host-jump and accessory genes. Isolates jump from host A to host B, accompanied with acquisition of gene B that is necessary for isolate adaptation in host B. Concerning the fate of ST398 accessory genes after a host-jump, we put forward two potential hypotheses (A): (I) A long-term co-evolution with host B to reshape accessory genes by losing gene A (blue arrow), as gene A is not necessary for isolate survival in host B. In this case, the accessory genes of isolates in host A are distinguishable from that in host B (see top left and bottom right plots), and the accessory genes are host-specific. (II) There is a jump back to host A or jump spillover to a third host C shortly afterwards (green arrows). In this case, isolates will carry several sets of accessory genes that are adaptation-relevant separately in different host species, and thus the accessory genes would be barely host-specific. Gene content of isolates is simplified to highlight the host adaptation-relevant genes and their acquisition and loss. The relationship between the diversity of accessory genes and the duration of frequent host-jumps (B). The accessory gene pool would substantially expand during the initial emergence of frequent host jumps, and subsequently become relatively stable when it has disseminated to most of the possible host species.

Figure 2

A global One Health atlas of *S. aureus* ST398. Sample collection in the study (left) and the geographic distribution of global ST398 (right). A total of 1079 isolate genomes with available collection locations, time and host species are included in this study.

Figure 3

The global profiles of ST398 accessory genomes. Antibiotic resistance genes, virulence genes and KEGG pathways (A) and the total gene number dynamics (B) in the global accessory gene pools. In each category (A), only top 5 taxa are shown. The successions of antibiotic resistance (C), virulence factor (D), host species number (E) and KEGG pathway genes (F) across different periods. The lines between periods show the persistence of the same genes in both periods, and are sized by the numbers of the

persisted genes. Distance-based redundancy analysis (G) shows the explanations of collection country, years and host species, and their joint explanation to the global profiles of accessory genomes. The distribution proportion of ST398 across different host species in different periods (H). The “*” along host species indicates a significant change of proportions between recent periods of 2011-2015 and 2016-2021, evaluated by Fisher's test.

Figure 4

Potential transfer of ST398 in global. Pies are colored by the proportions of human-isolates and animal-isolates, and sized by the number of isolates collected in specific regions. Two isolates from two different continents are assumed to be similar and a connection between them is generated, if their Mash distance is less than 0.0005. The number of such connections is represented by the width of the lines between continents, and the lines are colored by the proportions of connections between human-isolates and animal-isolates. The embedded subfigure shows the details of isolate distribution in Europe. Each pie represents a country/region, and is located in the map by the longitude and latitude information of the capital of the country.

Figure 5

Host-exclusive genetic elements. The heatmap (A) shows the host-exclusive antibiotic resistance genes, virulence factors, insertion sequences, phages and plasmids. The cells are colored by the numbers of isolates harboring host-exclusive taxa. The pathway-level frequencies (B) of host-exclusive functional genes are shown.

Figure 6

Accessory genes spread across different host species. The Bayesian source-tracker analysis quantifies the potential dissemination of ST398 accessory genomes across different host species (A). Lines are sized and colored by the estimated dissemination proportion of accessory genomes from the sourced host to the targeted host. Only lines with dissemination proportions > 5% are shown. The square represents host species and are sized by the numbers of inward arrows. Network analysis showing

potential transmission of accessory genomes of ST398 across host species (B). Nodes represent ST398 isolates and are sized by node degree (i.e., number of edges connected to the nodes). Edges indicate that the accessory genomes of two isolates are similar.

Figure 7

Phylogenetic diversification of global ST398 isolates. Phylogenetic maximum likelihood tree based on core genome isolates (A). Only top 10 subtypes are colored, and the other subtypes are colored in grey. SNPs

(Single-Nucleotide Polymorphisms) among consensus of different ST398 subtypes, and the number of such SNPs within genes of different pathways (B). Only the top 5 pathways are shown.

Figure 8

Maximum likelihood phylogeny based on core genome of ST398 isolated from patients. For patients who are sampled at multiple times, network linkages are from the earliest sampled isolates to subsequent isolates. Isolates from the other patients are colored by gray. For the collection country and body site, only the top five are colored separately. For the infection type, “NA” means isolates from patient who have not developed infection with ST398.

Supplementary Files

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